

Fatigue Damage Accumulation and Strength of CFRP Laminates with Different Moduli and Stacking Sequences

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ABSTRACT

Micro failure process of CFRP laminates with different moduli and stacking sequences are presented in this report. Cross-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates, which were reinforced by PAN based and pitch based carbon fibers, were used in this study. Static tension and fatigue tension were applied to coupon specimens. Matrix cracking in 90 degree layers and edge delamination were observed by using acoustic emission(AE), microscope and ultrasonic C-scan instruments. It was observed that high amplitude acoustic emissions corresponds to matrix cracking in the 90 degree layers. The quasi-isotropic laminates with high modulus (pitch based) carbon fiber show better fatigue resistance than those with the medium modulus (PAN based) carbon fiber. Furthermore, area of delamination and crack density were related to stiffness degradation, and delamination onset under tension fatigue can be predicted by using strain energy release rate.

Keyword : CFRP, Fatigue, Matrix crack, Edge delamination, AE, C-scan, High moduli, Energy release rate, Stacking sequence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Degradation of mechanical properties and ultimate strength of polymer composite under fatigue loading is an important issue for reliable composite structure. Fatigue strength and durability dependent on the stacking sequences and lamina orthotropy. Commonly observed micro fracture processes of laminated coupon specimens are transverse lamina cracking, local and edge delaminations.

In general, the initial failure, which is commonly transverse lamina cracking in the multi-directional reinforced laminate, initiates at low stress level, and cumulative failure leads to edge delaminations[1,2,3]. Fracture mechanics analyses of delaminations have been shown to provide generic characterization of delamination onset and growth[4,5,6].

In this paper, effects of stacking sequence and lamina orthotropy on static micro failure process are examined first using AE instrument and microscope. Next, the influence of high tensile and high modulus carbon fiber on quasi-isotropic laminates under tensile loading are investigated. The failure process are observed by using ultrasonic C-scan method, and delamination onset is considered.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

In order to estimate the delamination onset in the laminated composite plate, O'Brien[5] has proposed a simple equation for energy release rate calculation.

$$G = \frac{\epsilon^2 t_{LAM}}{2} (E_{LAM} + E^*) \quad (1)$$

Where, E_{LAM} and E^* are axial modulus before and after delamination, respectively, t_{LAM} is laminate thickness and e is uniaxial applied strain. when the energy release rate, G , reaches the critical values, G_c , the delamination is assumed to propagate in the laminate. By transforming Eq. (1) into stress based equation, we obtain Eq. (2).

$$G = \frac{\sigma^2 t_{LAM}}{2E_{LAM}^2} (E_{LAM} + E^*) \quad (2)$$

Eq. (2) indicates a guideline for delamination prevention approach. First, (a) to increase the interlaminar fracture toughness, G_c , second, (b) to decrease the anisotropic mismatch ($E_{LAM} - E^*$), and third, (c) to increase the lamina modulus E_{LAM} . The first approach (a) have been well discussed in many papers related to the toughened polymer composites. The second and third approach (b) and (c) are discussed in the present paper.

In order to avoid the matrix cracking in the 90 degree layer, it might be efficient to reduce the axial strain by increasing the axial elastic modulus. The effect of the axial modulus on the matrix cracking process is also present interest. The lamina strain and stress was calculated based on the lamination theory.

3. MATERIALS AND SPECIMENS

Two types of carbon fiber, PAN based medium modulus fiber T300 (Toray Industries, Inc.) and pitch based high modulus fiber XN40 (Nippon oil Inc.), were used in this study. The properties of these fibers are listed in Table 1. Though the tensile strength is almost the same, there is a big difference in tensile modulus between these fibers.

Four kinds of laminates A,B,C and D were used in the present study. Laminate A and B are PAN based fiber T300 reinforced 182°C(360°F) cured epoxy 3631 with different stacking sequences of $(0/90)_8$, and $(45/0/-45/90)_8$, respectively. Laminate C and D are quasi-isotropic $(45/0/-45/90)_8$ laminates with 121°C(250°F) cure epoxy resin 25CL reinforced by PAN based T300 and pitch based XN40, respectively. The nominal fiber volume fraction of the four laminates was about 60%.

The tensile test specimens were cut from the laminated plates by a diamond wheel. The specimens were 250mm long and 25mm wide. The specimen edges were well polished for easy inspection of matrix cracking and edge delamination. For the tensile tests, GFRP end-tabs were bonded to the specimens with epoxy adhesive to reinforce the gripping area. For Acoustic Emission(AE) experiments, two layers of sandpaper were wrapped around the ends of the specimen to avoid unnecessary noise emission. The first layer was #1000 sandpaper and the second layer was #800 sandpaper

Table 1 Materials properties of T300 and XN40 fibers.

		T300(PAN)	XN40(Pitch)
Tensile strength	(MPa)	3530	3530
Tensile modulus	(GPa)	230	390
Ultimate strain	(%)	1.5	0.9
Specific gravity	(g/cm ³)	1.76	2.12
Filament diameter	(μm)	7	10

4. EXPERIMENT

First, static tensile tests were carried out by using an Instron type testing machine and an AE instrument (PAC, Locan-AT) with a 150kHz resonant transducer. Crosshead rate was 0.5mm/min and a pair of air-assisted gripping fixtures were used for the test. AE activity and the density of matrix crack were measured in relation to the loading history.

Next, fatigue tests were carried out by using two different testing systems, the Instron type testing machine and an electro-hydraulic testing machine. Quasi-static repeated tensile load was applied on the specimens with the Instron type testing machine at a crosshead rate of 3mm/min. The stiffness

degradation was measured under cyclic loading.

High cycle tension fatigue tests were carried out by using a load-controlled electro-hydraulic testing machine with a loading frequency of 5Hz, and the ratio of minimum to maximum load was taken as 0.1. The maximum fatigue cycles were limited to 10^6 . The axial elongation of the specimen was measured by an extensometer (MTS) of 100mm gage length. Matrix cracks and delamination were observed by removing the specimen from the testing machine and measuring by microscope similar to the static test. The delaminated area of the specimen was also measured by using ultrasonic C-scan instrument (PAC, ULTRAPAC II System with 10MHz sensor).

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Effect of Stacking Sequence on Static Fracture Process

Table 2 shows mean values of tensile properties for four types of laminates. Figure 1 shows the three dimensional diagram of load history and AE amplitude versus AE hits for the laminates $(0/90)_6s$, $(45/0/-45/90)_6s$ and $(45/0/-45/90)_s$. In case of the $(0/90)_6s$ laminate, the AE hits with amplitude above 80dB correspond to formation of a visual crack in the 90 degree layer, and also correspond to an emission of audible sounds.

In case of the $(45/0/-45/90)_6s$ laminate, the total number of cracks increased compared with the $(0/90)_6s$ laminate. The total AE hits were twice as many as the hits in the $(0/90)_6s$ laminate. It was obvious from the edge view of the specimen that the delamination between the -45 and the 90 degree layer initiates discontinuously from the matrix crack tip in the 90 degree layer and extends to the 0/-45 interlaminar. It seems that the sub-critical crack growth corresponds to the low amplitude AE hits.

In case of $(45/0/-45/90)_s$ laminate, edge delamination occurred between the -45 and the 90 degree layers. Matrix cracks were also detected in the 90 degree layer. It is known that the fracture of the edge delamination is a combination of mode I,II and III. Therefore, considerable AE is caused by the friction in the fracture surface, including the AE caused by delamination growth.

Table 2 Material specification of four types of laminates.

Fiber/matrix	Laminate A	Laminate B	Laminate C	Laminate D
	T300/3631	T300/3631	T300/25CL	XN/25CL
Stacking sequence	$(0/90)_6s$	$(45/0/-45/90)_6s$	$(45/0/-45/90)_s$	$(45/0/-45/90)_s$
Tensile strength (MPa)	171	253	509	536
Tensile modulus (GPa)	23.3	24.8	51.4	87.8
Thickness (mm)	1.85	2.37	0.96	0.88
Failure strain (%)	0.85	1.23	0.98	0.61

Fig. 1 Examples of time history of AE amplitude distribution of three different laminates.

(a) $(0/90)_6s$ (b) $(45/0/-45/90)_6s$ and (c) $(45/0/-45/90)_s$

Fig.2 Crack density versus strain plots for quasi-isotropic T300/25CL and XN40/25CL laminates under static tension test.

5.2 Effect of Lamina Orthotropy on the Static Fracture Process in Quasi-Isotropic Laminates

Quasi-isotropic $(45/0/-45/90)_s$ laminates of T300/25CL and XN40/25CL were investigated. Tensile strength of the T300/25CL is almost same as XN40/25CL, though the tensile moduli are different. The ultimate failure strains of T300/25CL and XN40/25CL are 0.98% and 0.61%, respectively. Figure 2 shows the change in crack density in the 90 degree layer observed at the edge of the specimen with the tensile strain. The matrix crack in XN40/25CL occur at a strain level of 0.2% and increase exponentially. On the other hand, matrix crack in T300/25CL occurs at a strain of approximately 0.7%. Large difference in the onset of matrix crack observed. Edge delamination initiates from the tip of the matrix crack at a matrix crack density level of 1mm^{-1} . Bonding strength and modulus mismatch between fiber and matrix may affect the laminate response in the transverse and interlaminar directions.

5.3 Stiffness Degradation under Quasi-Static Repeated Tensile Load

A preliminary fatigue test under load amplitude indicated that edge delamination easily initiates at the first stage of loading upto 100 cycles. The failure process within 100 loading cycles was examined in detail. Figure 3 represents the effect of the maximum stress to the ultimate tensile strength ratio, σ_{\max}/σ_u , on the history of stiffness degradation. Figure 4 shows the effect of stacking sequence in the change of stiffness under the two levels of applied load. The stiffness degradation of $(45/0/-45/90)_s$ depends on the stress level, and the values are between 2.2% and 3.2% at 70 cycles.

Stiffness degradation of the $(0/90)_s$ and the $(45/0/-45/90)_s$ laminates are steeper than that of $(45/0/-45/90)_s$ laminate. Thickness of 90 degree layers has a direct influence on stiffness reduction process, which is mainly controlled by matrix cracking.

Fig.3 Stiffness degradation as a function of load cycles for quasi-isotropic T300/25CL laminates.

Fig.4 Stiffness degradation as a function of load cycles for $(0/90)_s$ and $(45/0/-45/90)_s$ T300/3631 laminates.

5.4 High Cycle Fatigue Fracture Process in Quasi-Isotropic Laminates

Tensile fatigue process of quasi-isotropic (45/0/-45/90)_s laminates of T300/25CL and XN40/25CL were investigated in order to examine the effect of lamina orthotropy on fatigue life. The onset of matrix cracking and delamination, as well as breakage point, are plotted and interpolated on the stress versus cycle (S-N) diagrams as shown in Fig. 5.

In case of the T300/25CL laminate, strength reduction due to fatigue is observed over 5,000 cycles of loading. The slope of the interpolated line of the delamination onset is almost the same as the slope of matrix cracking onset, as well as that of breakage points. The fatigue fracture at the XN40/25CL laminate is not clear on the S-N diagram. Slope of the characteristic lines of the delamination onset of the T300/25CL laminates is similar to the slope of the XN40/25CL laminates.

The behavior of the cracking process observed on the specimen edge, begins from matrix cracks in the 90 degree layer. Next, the cracks connect with each other through between the -45 and the 90 degree layers resulting in delamination. The process is similar to static tensile behavior.

Figure 6 shows the crack density versus loading cycle diagram of T300/25CL and XN40/25CL, respectively. The loading condition is not exactly the same for the two laminates, namely the maximum stress to the stress of onset of matrix crack ratio, σ_{max}/σ_{mc} , is 0.78 for T300/25CL and 0.81 for XN40/25CL laminate. It shows a large difference in the tendency of cracking processes. The onset of matrix crack in T300/25CL is about 10^3 cycles and the crack density increases considerably with the loading cycle. On the other hand, the onset for XN40/25CL laminate is about 10^5 cycles and the crack density is at a low level during the test.

Stiffness degradation of the T300/25CL and XN40/25CL laminates was examined under the loading condition of the maximum load, σ_{max} , kept to 70% of the ultimate tensile strength, and the results are

Fig.5 Tension fatigue behavior of quasi-isotropic laminates.

Fig.6 Crack density versus tension fatigue cycles for quasi-isotropic T300/25CL and XN40/25CL laminates.

shown in Fig. 7. The two laminates represent the difference in characteristics, the onset cycles and the slope, on the normalized stiffness versus cycle curves. The cycle of degradation onset in the T300/25CL laminates is about 10 times larger than the XN40/25CL laminates, but the slope of the T300/25CL laminates is much larger than the slope of the XN40/25CL laminates.

Fig.7 Stiffness degradation as a function of load cycles for $(45/0/-45/90)_3$ laminates under σ_{max}/σ_u of 70%.

Fig.8 Ultrasonic C-scan images of quasi-isotropic laminates at several cycle numbers under σ_{max}/σ_u of 70%.
(a) T300/25CL (b) XN40/25CL

Fig.9 Normalized delamination area as a function of load cycles for quasi-isotropic T300/25CL and XN40/25CL laminates under σ_{max}/σ_u of 70%.

Fig.10 Critical maximum energy release rate at onset of delamination as a function of load cycle.

Figure 8 shows the changes in delaminated and non-delaminated area observed by using the ultrasonic C-scan method. The maximum stress is 70% of the ultimate tensile strength, the condition is the same as the previous figures. It was confirmed from a calibrated scan area that the border of non-delaminated and delaminated areas is identified as the reflected level of 25dB.

The correlation between the rate of delamination and the fatigue cycles is shown in Fig.9. The onset of delamination for the XN40/25CL laminates is earlier than the T300/25CL laminates, but it is obvious that XN40/25CL laminate has better resistance against delamination growth. Figure 10 shows the correlation between critical energy release rate G and fatigue cycles at delamination onset. The two curves of the T300/25CL and XN40/25CL laminates are almost identical, and the result might indicate the delamination fatigue process are controlled by the same fracture criterion, $G=G_c(N)$.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the effects of stacking sequence and lamina orthotropy on the static micro failure process were examined. Next, the influences of medium modulus and high modulus carbon fiber on quasi-isotropic laminates were investigated under tensile fatigue loading. The results are summarized as follows.

1. Matrix cracks in the thick inner 90 degree layer of laminates affect stiffness degradation, and the onset of the cracks corresponds to the AE activity.

2. In spite of laminates having similar tensile strength, the onset of matrix crack and delamination of quasi-isotropic laminates with high modulus carbon fiber occurs at low stress level under static loading.
3. Quasi-isotropic laminates of high modulus carbon fiber have better tension fatigue resistance than laminates with medium modulus carbon fiber.
4. It is possible to estimate the onset of the delamination by using energy release rate G .

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